

**Al₂O₃ preform evaluation and mechanical properties of Squeeze casting
Al₂O₃/AC8A Composites**

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the Al₂O₃ preform properties in order to predict fabrication process of sound Al₂O₃/AC8A composites prior to squeeze casting. Also, composites was examined for mechanical property and interfacial reaction after squeeze casting. Evaluation for the preform was to focus on the pore size, pore distribution, distribution of binder and compression property of the preform. It was found that pore size distribution and binder distribution on the fiber in preforms such as Toyota and Inha A are homogeneous, whereas those of Inha B preform are inhomogeneous. In compression strength, Toyota and Inha A preforms showed higher values compared with Inha B preform. Macroscopic observation indicated that Inha B preform is remarkably deformed along the vertical direction, whereas the another preforms are not deformed after squeeze casting. In hardness, it was shown that value of the Al₂O₃/AC8A composites fabricated by Inha A preform is much higher than that of the AC8A matrix. After thermal exposure, interfacial reaction zone was found to be formed with 0.5 μ m thickness at the interface between Al₂O₃ fiber and AC8A matrix at 400°C for 150hrs.

Keywords : Al₂O₃ short fiber, preform evaluation, squeeze casting, thermal exposure, interfacial reaction

1. INTRODUCTION

Al matrix composites by squeeze casting is now well known for its suitability for mass production. A large amount of works have already been performed, mainly in industry, to improve the processing conditions and to extend the possibility of squeeze casting.[1-8] However, the diversity of preform natures and part shape as well as the conception of new processing techniques related to squeeze casting require many preliminary experiments which are particularly time consuming. It is very important to successfully squeeze cast without

deformation of preform under the optimum cast condition. Therefore, the availability of preform evaluation prior to squeeze casting should be helpful to reduce expenses devoted to the optimization of processing conditions. However, there are not published works on evaluation method for preform before Squeeze casting. The main purpose of this study was to offer fundamental guide line for evaluation of Al_2O_3 preforms made by various process prior to Squeeze casting in order to predict sound $Al_2O_3/AC4C$ composites fabrication process. Also, these composites were examined for mechanical properties and interfacial reactions after squeeze casting.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Al_2O_3 preforms used are Toyota (V_f 10%), Inha. A (V_f 10%) and Inha. B (V_f 10%). Inha. A and B preforms were fabricated by using different binder, respectively. Figure 1 shows a schematic of preforms (Inha A and Inha B) made by pressure forming. Toyota preform is fabricated by suction forming. AC8A alloy was used for the matrix. Pore size and pore distribution in the preform were measured by Autopore-9220 Micrometrics apparatus. Pore size relates to the infiltration pressure of mercury by the followign equation.

$$P = \frac{-2 \gamma \cos \theta}{r}$$

P : pressure

γ : surface tension

θ : contact angle between mercury and solid material

r : pore radius

Al_2O_3 fiber orientation and binder distribution on the fiber were observed by SEM. The size of measured preform was $10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{mm}^3$. Compression test for evaluation of preform strength was carried out by Tinius Olsen 500 tensile test machine.

In squeeze casting process, preheated preforms were inserted into the mold heated at 250°C . Melting Al alloy was poured into 750°C into the mold and then pressed under 80 MPa. Punch moving speed was 1.5mm/sec, holding time 10 sec after pressure. After squeeze casting, the degree of preform deformation was observed after vertically cutting cast specimen. The only $Al_2O_3/AC8A$ composites fabricated by Inha A preform was used for interfacial reaction and mechanical property. Thermal exposure was conducted at 300°C and 400°C up to 150hr. After thermal exposure, observation and analysis for the interface were examined by STEM (CM 30 Phillips). Hardness (H_{RB}) was examined by Rockwell Hardness (DYH-100).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In general, two methods of fabrication include press forming and suction forming. In

both cases, short fibers are mixed homogeneously with water accompanied by a small addition of binder. The chopped fibers are piled up around the filter in a suction forming operation to form a preform. During press forming, the slurry is poured into the mold and dewatering is conducted while the final preform is shaped. Here, it is very important to homogeneous distribution of the fiber and enough strength of preform in order to infiltrate the molten metal without excessive deformation of the preform when the fiber preform is less than 10% of volume fraction fiber. Figure 2 shows SEM photographs of outersection of various preforms. It was revealed that in outersection of the preforms, distribution and orientation of the fiber in all preforms are arranged with three dimension. However, Al_2O_3 fibers in preforms of Toyota and Inha B were found to be locally entangled. In Binder distribution, the fiber surface in Toyota and Inha A preforms is uniformly coated with binder material as shown in figure 2 (a) and (b), whereas each individual fiber in Inha B preform is surrounded by a large amount of binder, indicating no coating on the fiber as shown in figure 2 (c). In the innersection of the preform, it could be seen that fiber distribution and orientation in all the preforms are homogeneous as well as outersection of the preform as shown in figure 3 (a), (b) and (c). As shown in figure 3 (a) and (b), it was observed that distribution of binder on the fiber in Toyota and Inha A preforms is uniform, being evident from the roughness of fiber surface coated with binder material. However, distribution of binder on the Al_2O_3 fiber in Inha B preform was found to be remarkably inhomogeneous, indicating the absence of binder material on the fiber surface as shown in figure 3 (c). Figure 4 shows pore size and pore distribution in various preforms. From this figure, it was found that the pore size of all the preforms is distributed in the range of $9\mu m$ to $400\mu m$ diameter. In particular, pore size in Toyota and Inha A preforms is largely distributed in the range of size less than $40\mu m$, whereas a large amount of pore size in Inha B preform is distributed in the range of size more than $40\mu m$. Virtually, it was approved that distribution of pore size in Toyota and Inha A preforms is homogeneous as a whole, comparing with Inha B preform which pore size is broadly distributed in the whole range. In compression strength, Inha B preform showed low value compare with the another preforms such as Toyota and Inha A preforms as shown in figure 5. Remarkable difference of compression strength between Inha B and another preforms may be due to the factors such as pore size distribution and binder distribution. It was observed that Toyota and Inha A preforms were not deformed after squeeze casting, whereas Inha B preform was deformed upto 15.29% of total volume. Thus, it is evident from that preform property affects on the deformation of preform during squeeze casting. It was noticed that the hardness of the composites is greater than that of AC8A matrix as shown in figure 6. After thermal exposure, both the composites and the matrix tended to decrease after 50 hrs. at $400^\circ C$. Hardness of the composites is two times higher than that of matrix at $400^\circ C$ for 150 hrs. This is due to the existence of the hard Al_2O_3 fiber in the matrix.

Figure 7 shows the variation of tensile strength of $Al_2O_3/AC8A$ composites after

exposure times at 300°C and 400°C. From this figure, tensile strength of the composites was found to remarkably decrease upto 50hrs at 400°C and linearly decrease upto 150hrs, as exposure time and temperature increases. After thermal exposure, strength reduction of the composites results from the softening of the matrix and formation of interfacial reaction zone. In particular, STEM observation for interfacial reaction zone indicated that interfacial reaction zone is formed with 0.1 μm thickness between AC8A matrix and Al_2O_3 fiber after thermal exposure for 150 hrs. at 300°C and then grows upto 0.5 μm thickness at 400°C for 150hrs. as shown in figure 8 (b) and (c). However, interfacial reaction zone is not formed at interface of as-squeeze cast composites as shown in figure 8 (a). Also, STEM analysis for interfacial reaction zone revealed that reaction zone contains of Al, Mg and P constant as shown in figure 9. P element may be considered to be residual element in binder material.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. It was found that pore size distribution and binder distribution on the fiber in the preforms such as Toyota and Inha A are homogeneous, whereas those of Inha B preform are inhomogeneous. In compression strength of preforms, Toyota and Inha A preforms showed higher values compared with Inha B preform.
2. It was revealed that Inha B preform is remarkably deformed along the vertical direction, whereas another preforms were not deformed after squeeze casting. This is due to factors such as inhomogeneous distribution of pore size, binder distribution and poor compression strength of preform.
3. In hardness, it was shown that value of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{AC8A}$ composites fabricated by Inha A preform is much higher than that of the AC8A matrix.
4. After thermal exposure, interfacial reaction zone was found to be formed at the interface with the thickness of 0.5 μm at 400°C for 150hrs. STEM observation revealed that interfacial reaction layer contains of Al, Mg and P content.

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Figure 1 Schematic illustration of preform made by pressure forming.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Figure 2 SEM photographs of outersection of preforms.
(a) TOYOTA (b) INHA A (c) INHA B

Figure 3 SEM photographs of innersection of preforms.
(a) TOYOTA (b) INHA A (c) INHA B

Figure 4 Pore diameter and distribution of various preforms.

Figure 5 Compression strength of various preforms.

Figure 6 The variation of hardness of $Al_2O_3/AC8A$ composites with various exposure times at 300°C and 400°C.

Figure 7 The variation of tensile strength of $Al_2O_3/AC8A$ composites with various exposure times at 300°C and 400°C.

Figure 8 TEM micrographs for the vicinity of interface in thermal exposed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{AC8A}$ composites.

(a) as-cast (b) 300°C/150hrs. (c) 400°C/150hrs.

Figure 9 STEM analysis for interfacial reaction zone in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{AC8A}$ composites.